

Some Peculiarities of the Isoconversional Methods

Peter Šimon, Tibor Dubaj, Zuzana Cibulková and Anna Vykydalová

Institute of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology, Radlinského 9, SK-812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia (E-mail: peter.simon@stuba.sk)

ABSTRACT

Solid state processes are extensively studied by thermoanalytical methods. Mechanisms of these processes are very often unknown or too complicated to be characterised by a simple kinetic model. They tend to occur in multiple steps that have different rates. To describe their kinetics, isoconversional methods are often used.

The principal idea of isoconversional methods is very simple, there are only two basic assumptions [1]:

(i) Rate of the processes in condensed state is generally a function of temperature and conversion:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \Phi(T, \alpha) \quad (1)$$

The isoconversional methods employ the assumption that the function Φ in Eq. (1) can be expressed as a product of two functions independent of each other, the first one, $k(T)$, depending solely on temperature T and the other one, $f(\alpha)$, depending solely on the conversion of the process, α :

$$\Phi(T, \alpha) = k(T)f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

Combining Eqs.(1) and (2), the rate of the process can then be formally described by a single-step rate equation [2] even though the kinetics of a complex process should be described by a set of kinetic equations. Eq.(3) is called the general/generalized kinetic equation. It is a mathematical tool enabling to described the kinetics of a complex process in a simple and feasible manner

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

(ii) The kinetic parameters are obtained from a set of kinetic runs from the dependences of time vs. temperature (for isothermal measurements), temperature vs. heating rate (for integral and incremental methods with linear heating rate) or from reaction rate vs. temperature (for the differential Friedman method). The evaluation is carried out at the fixed conversion α [1].

The isoconversional methods can be roughly divided into three groups, i.e. the integral, incremental and differential methods [1]. The most popular and most employed are the integral isoconversional methods. Very often, as a result of kinetic analysis, the kinetic parameters obtained appear to depend on the conversion. In this case, the kinetic analysis is mathematically incorrect and extrapolated approximations may lead to nonsensical dependences, such as shown in [3] (see Fig.1). In such a case, application of the incremental methods is advisable [4].

Another quite strange thing with the isoconversional methods is that the experimental kinetic data can be described equivalently by several temperature functions, not only by the Arrhenius function (see Fig.2). First, who realized that fact and justified it, was Laidler [5]. For the evaluation of kinetic data and further application of the kinetic parameters obtained, the Bethelot-Hood temperature function appeared to be most suitable [6].

$$k(T) = A_k e^{DT} \quad (4)$$

Fig.1: Dependence of conversion on time calculated using the kinetic parameters from thermogravimetric measurements with linear heating for the drug HI-6.

Keywords: extrapolation, isoconversional, kinetics, solid state, thermal analysis, temperature function.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

Financial support from the Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV-15-0124) is also gratefully acknowledged.

References:

- [1] P.Šimon, J.Therm.Anal.Calorim. 76 (2004) 123-132: Isoconversional methods: Fundamentals, meaning and application.
- [2] P.Šimon, J.Therm.Anal.Calorim. 82 (2005) 651-657: Considerations on the single-step kinetics approximation.
- [3] P.Šimon, P.Thomas, T.Dubaj, Z.Cibulková, A.Peller, M.Veverka, J Therm Anal Calorim 115 (2014) 853–859: The mathematical incorrectness of the integral isoconversional methods in case of variable activation energy and the consequences.
- [4] T.Dubaj, Z.Cibulková, P.Šimon, J. Comput.Chemistry 36 (2015) 392–398: An incremental isoconversional method for kinetic analysis based on the orthogonal distance regression.
- [5] P.Šimon, T.Dubaj, Z.Cibulková, J Therm Anal Calorim 120 (2015) 231–238: Equivalence of the Arrhenius and ,non-Arrhenian temperature functions in the temperature range of measurement.
- [6] P.Šimon, D.Hynek, M.Malíková, Z.Cibulková, J Therm Anal Calorim. 93 (2008) 817–821: Extrapolation of accelerated thermooxidative tests to lower temperatures applying non-Arrhenius temperature functions.